

ISic2754

I.Sicily inscription 2754

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

oracle

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2011-06-16; 2013-10-02 (Prag)

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance

Found by a local farmer in the area of Colle Orbo c.1968

Coordinates

37.054649, 14.899828

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 66527

Physical Description

Five joining fragments of the upper part of a thick limestone slab, intact on the top, left and right, broken across the lower part, with damage to the lower right margin higher than on the left, beginning from line 6 of the text. The rear of the stone is finished also. Fragment A (upper left): max W 20.5 cm, max H. 19, D 6.9-8.1; fragment B (upper right): max W 17 cm, max H 18.5, D 7.3-8.5; fragment C (lower left): max W 14.5, max H 11.5, D 6.8-7.0; fragment D (lower middle): max W 3.5cm, max H 3, D (damaged) 3.5; fragment E (lower right) missing.

Dimensions

Height 27.5 cm

Width 35 cm

Depth 8.5 cm

Layout

The left margin of the text is carefully justified, but the right margin is very uneven, with several extensive vacats at line end.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Regular small letters of generally consistent size, deeply cut with pronounced terminal serifs on some strokes. Alpha is broad with straight bar, occasional extension of apex; beta appears open with rounded but not fully circular equal loops; epsilon has shorter middle bar, and upper and lower strokes often curve outwards at the ends; theta is ovoid with complete horizontal bar; kappa has short, equal length tails; mu has middle strokes joining well above the line; nu has the lower right angle above the line with shorter right vertical stroke; omicron is smaller and above the line; pi has shorter right vertical; rho is closed with generally circular eye; sigma has upper and lower horizontals curving slightly outwards at the ends, and the middle strokes often form into a single curving stroke; phi has a rounded eye, with the vertical extended, up to 17mm; psi has extended vertical and straight arms; omega is small, rounded, above the line, and open, with generally horizontal tail strokes.

Letter heights:

Line 1-19: 5-7 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Τετραλεα δ' αὐτὸ,μ προσέφημ· Πάτερ, ἦλυθα τιμὴν(vac.undefinied)
2. εἴ τινά μοι δοίης· τὰ δ' ἐφήμερά μ' οὐδ' ἰσάασιν(vac.undefinied)
3. ὦλλοις δ' εἰσὶ τεχνῶν ἐύ[ρ]είματα, καρποὶ ἅπασιν,(vac.undefinied)
4. μνημείων ὅσοι τιμαὶ καὶ ἄγεια σέβουσιν.(vac.undefinied)
5. Μαίη δ'οὐδ' ἐφορᾷ με μόνημ, πάντ[ω]ς δ' ἀγέραστος.
6. τόσσ' ἐφάμην· ὁ δὲ νεῦσε κάρα καὶ θεΐά μοι εὕδα·
7. οὐδεὶς ἀθανάτωμ φθαρέει βροτόν, οὐδ' ἀνελήσει
8. ἢ σὺ, τέκος, καὶ Φοῖβος ἐκαβόλος ἰῶι,(vac.undefinied)
9. οὐδ' αὐτῶι θεμιτόν τιν' ὀλεῖν, οἷ χρησμῶι ἔπονταν.
10. ἄλ[λο]ςᾶφ]ωνα κατ' ἄστρα φυέντων τῶ μόρος· εἴ τι[ς]
11. σοί [τιπρόσεισ]ι κράτει, τιμῆι δέ τοι οὔτις ὄμ[οιος]
12. ἦρως, [π]ροσθεμένη Νύμφας ἐπὶ πᾶσι[ν]όρεσσιν].
13. Μαίη, δ' οὐ χρησμ[ού]ς σοι ἔ[φαινε]ν---
14. εἰ δ' αὖ καὶ τι θέλεις, χρηζί[ε]---
15. ἐνθεάσασ' ἀβροτῆ ν[υκτὶ]---
16. ἔκτοσε θυη εμε---
17. ὄν δὴ ἐποψ---
18. ταῦτα γ---
19. []---

Apparatus

Text after Manganaro 1992, but checked against the stone by autopsy (Prag)

The top of either a Φ or a Ψ is visible in approximately the fifth position of the line

Translation

Commentary

Of the five fragments, three are large (a, b, c) and two very small (d and e); the smallest (e), from the bottom edge of the join between the two principal fragments, is currently unlocated and not with the other fragments. The text should be considered alongside ISic3367 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3367>] ; it was recovered together with that piece (although there is no evidence of how close the association was). The letter forms are effectively identical on the two pieces, probably cut by the same hand.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645156

EDCS 71000508

PHI 333744

PHI 333745

PHI 331329

PHI 332317

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic2754. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4355061>

Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014